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Traditional Budgeting And Performance Of Auditing Firms In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the traditional budgeting and performance of auditing firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives were to determine the effect of incremental budgeting on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State; Ascertain the effect of capital budgeting on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State. This research work will be anchored on the Risk Based Budgeting Theory. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were generated from primary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected audit firms in Anambra State. The population of the study was one hundred and fifty-seven (157) staff. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Incremental budgeting has no significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State (t, 0.558, p, 790); capital budgeting has significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State (t, 2.342, p, .000). The study concludes that traditional budgeting remains relevant to auditing firms; its effectiveness depends largely on the type of budgeting practice adopted. The study recommends that; Auditing firms in Anambra State should minimize excessive dependence on incremental budgeting. Management should avoid merely adjusting previous budgets without critically evaluating current operational needs, market conditions, and firm-specific challenges. Auditing firms should place greater emphasis on long-term investment planning. Proper evaluation techniques such as net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), and payback period should be consistently applied when making investment decisions to ensure optimal allocation of scarce resources

Keywords: traditional budgeting, auditing firms, incremental budgeting, capital budgeting

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Budgeting is a critical financial planning tool that enables organizations to allocate resources, set performance targets, and manage operations effectively. In today's dynamic and competitive business environment, especially in emerging economies like Nigeria, effective budgeting practices have become vital to ensuring corporate sustainability and enhanced performance (Abiji et al 2024). For manufacturing companies, budgeting is not just an accounting exercise but a strategic function that guides decision-making and long-term growth. The significance of budgeting is more pronounced in volatile environments, such as Rivers State in Nigeria, where industrial firms operate amid macroeconomic uncertainty, infrastructural deficiencies, and regulatory constraints (Mubaraq & Oladipo 2022).

Budgeting is a fundamental tool in organizational financial management, used worldwide to plan, control, and evaluate financial activities. In its traditional form, budgeting typically involves preparing financial plans based on historical figures and fixed incremental adjustments for the upcoming period without

necessarily linking them to strategic performance targets or outputs (Abiji et al 2024). Traditional budgeting in many Nigerian organizations public and private alike remains largely incremental, top-down and compliance-oriented, emphasizing rigid allocation of resources rather than performance outcomes. While this approach provides a sense of control and predictability, it has been criticized for its lack of flexibility, limited capacity to drive innovation, and insufficient alignment with organizational goals. Research outside Nigeria has highlighted how traditional budgeting may constrain managerial decision-making and limit responsiveness to changing internal and external conditions (Mudiri, & Mwengei 2020). In the Nigerian context, budgeting plays a central role in the management of scarce resources across corporate and public sectors. Studies have shown significant challenges in budget preparation and implementation, including poor adherence to approved budget provisions, weak financial control mechanisms, and accountability deficits in government parastatals and corporate entities. These challenges often result in delays in budget execution, misallocation of resources, and financial improprieties, undermining the potential benefits of budgetary planning and control (Onyebuchi,2022).

Audit quality is a critical aspect of financial governance and accountability. It refers to the degree to which financial audits are conducted in accordance with established auditing standards, producing reliable, objective, and timely assurance on the fairness of financial reports (Ukutegebe & Ehiedu, 2025). High audit quality is essential for stakeholder confidence, effective corporate governance, and the credibility of financial information used in decision-making. Empirical studies from Nigeria indicate that audit quality impacts various aspects of financial reporting and organizational performance, including mitigating earnings management, enhancing financial reporting reliability, and reducing agency conflicts between managers and stakeholders (Olaniyan & Efuntade, 2020).

Despite extensive research on budgeting practices and audit quality separately, there is a gap in understanding how traditional budgeting practices influence audit quality specifically in the Nigerian environment. Traditional budgeting, with its rigid planning and control focus, may affect the audit process by shaping internal controls, financial documentation practices, and the predictability of financial performance (Egbunike & Unamma, 2017). When budgets are poorly aligned with organizational activities or when they promote mechanical compliance without critical evaluation, auditors may face constraints in accessing relevant information, evaluating risk effectively, and forming high-quality audit opinions. The relationship between budgeting practices and audit outcomes thus warrants careful empirical investigation, especially given Nigeria's ongoing efforts to strengthen financial governance and transparency across sectors Owoloabi et al (2020). Understanding the effect of traditional budgeting on audit quality can provide valuable insights into how budgeting reforms, such as participative budgeting or performance budgeting, might enhance the effectiveness of both planning and auditing functions in Nigerian organizations.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Traditional budgeting remains the dominant financial planning and control mechanism in many Nigerian organizations, including public institutions and private sector firms. This budgeting approach is typically characterized by incremental budgeting, rigid annual budget cycles, line-item controls, and an emphasis on cost containment rather than strategic value creation. While traditional budgeting is designed to promote financial discipline and accountability, its continued application in a dynamic and risk-prone business environment has raised concerns about its implications for audit quality in Nigeria.

Audit quality is critical to the credibility of financial reporting, the prevention of fraud, and the enhancement of stakeholder confidence in organizations. In Nigeria, recurring cases of financial misstatements, audit failures, public sector fund mismanagement, and corporate scandals have intensified concerns about the effectiveness of audit processes. Despite the existence of regulatory frameworks such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) Act and professional standards issued by ICAN and ANAN, questions persist regarding the extent to which internal control systems, particularly budgeting practices support or undermine the quality of audits.

Traditional budgeting may adversely affect audit quality by encouraging budgetary slack, earnings manipulation, and rigid spending patterns that obscure true financial performance. The pressure to meet

predetermined budget targets may also influence management behavior, leading to intentional misclassification of expenditures or suppression of relevant financial information, thereby increasing audit risk. Furthermore, the inflexibility of traditional budgeting systems may limit auditors' ability to respond effectively to emerging risks, complex transactions, and real-time financial anomalies, especially in an economy characterized by inflation, policy instability, and technological change.

Although several studies in Nigeria have examined budgeting practices in relation to organizational performance, financial control, and accountability, empirical evidence on the specific effect of traditional budgeting on audit quality remains limited and fragmented. This gap in the literature creates uncertainty about whether traditional budgeting enhances audit effectiveness by strengthening controls or weakens audit quality by promoting compliance-driven rather than risk-based auditing. Consequently, there is a need for a systematic investigation into the effect of traditional budgeting on audit quality in Nigeria, with a view to providing evidence-based insights for policymakers, professional bodies, auditors, and organizational managers seeking to improve financial transparency and audit outcomes.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine the traditional budgeting and performance of auditing firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study were as follow:

1. Determine the effect of incremental budgeting on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State
2. Ascertain the effect of capital budgeting on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Budgeting

Budgets play a vital role in short-term planning and control within organizations (Anthony et al., 2007; Otley, 1999; Bergmann et al. 2020). Budget has long been and will remain an essential tool for organizations (Duan et al., 2022), serving as a key method for evaluating performance efficiency (Her et al., 2019). Budgeting process entails the organized planning, management, and assessment of financial resources and activities to meet business goals (Takwa et al. 2024). Budgeting involves forecasting a company's future financial needs (Garrison et al., 2003). A budget serves as a detailed plan that outlines how resources will be obtained and utilized over a specific time frame. Moreover, budget process helps businesses to uplift the performance through several means.

Budgeting refer to the methods, procedures, and systems organizations use to plan, allocate, monitor, and control financial resources over a specific period. It encompasses the entire budgeting lifecycle from strategic planning to performance evaluation and is essential for financial discipline, resource optimization, and goal achievement (Wonder, et al 2018). Budgeting can be described as a system of controlling cost which embraces the preparation of budget, coordinating the department and establishing responsibility, comparing actual performance with budgeted and acting upon results to achieve maximum performance (Egbunike & Unamma, 2017).

2.1.2 Incremental budgeting

This is the traditional approach that uses the current year estimates of income and expenditure as the basis for determining the budget for the year. It is normally used in public sector and it has the misfortune of carrying over the inadequacy of yester-years into subsequent year budgets as it only increases the current period figure with what the establishment thinks is the inflationary premium for next year financial period. Abdullahi (2007) confirms that the incremental budgeting approach is used extensively in government parastatals because of its simplicity.

Before any annual budget in a government could be contemplated or prepared, a base of such budget must be established from where the process will commence. With the base, common starting point for the preparation of the coming year budget is the current year's budget, incorporating the current level of operating activity and current budgeted allowances for current activities. This are then adjusted for expected changes that may likely occur during the next year. This approach is referred to as incremental

or traditional budgeting. This is because the budget processes is concern mainly with the increment (and hardly decrease) in operations or expenditure which would take place during the next budget year (Watoseninyi, 1999). Increment means always there is an increase (Abdullahi, 2007).

For instance, the allowance for budgeted expenditure may be based on the previous budgeted allowance plus an increase to cover any expected increase in prices. Abdullahi, (2011) sees incremental budgeting system as a budget prepared using a previous period's budget or actual performance as a basis with incremental amounts added for the new budget period. The system is only seen as a tradition, no more. Abdullahi, (2007) Confirms that the incremental budgeting approach is used extensively in government parastatals because of its simplicity.

2.1.3 Capital budgeting

Capital budgeting decisions aim at identification and allocation of funds by an organization into profitable projects. It enhances financial performance of an organization by providing suitable rationale of selection viable investment projects that maximizes the wealth of its shareholders (Adu, and Ajigbotoso, 2024). Capital budgeting is the most important function of finance since the results continue for a long time and the firm may lose some of its flexibility. It defines firm strategic direction because to invest in new products, services or markets it must be preceded by capital expenditure. Capital budgeting enables organizations to evaluate various investment options for optimal shareholders' wealth creation (Abor, 2005).

Capital budgeting involves current decisions that have a long term effect on an enterprise. The nature of capital budgeting consists of heavy investments being made and existence of a time gap between initial outlay and return of the investment (Adu, 2016). Capital budgeting decisions involve the process of determining projects with positive net present values and investing in them. Capital budgeting decisions involve allocation of significant corporate resources and the decisions are mostly irreversible or where reversible the company incurs a significant loss (Brian, 2012).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Risk Based Budgeting Theory

Risk based budgeting approach was developed by Maillard, Roncalli and Teiletche in 2010. The theory focus on the consideration of risk in the budgeting process. Risk Budgeting is the process of decomposing the combined risk of a portfolio investment process into its constituents on a quantitative basis. This risk-based investment strategy puts diversification of risk at the heart of the investment process. This risk based budgeting theory relates to the study as it suggest the inclusion of risk indecision of budgeting in order to maximize return contributed by budgeting approaches. Lack of skills inhibits the use of budget (Phenya, 2011). Proper and careful consideration of risks in the budgeting process increases uniformity in various aspects of budgets. Planning and projections done in budget processes has an effect on budgeting goals and objectives.

According to Harvard Business Review (2011), it is assessed that organizations with a Chief Risk Officer have considerably more extensive risk planning than other companies. MSEs with portfolio investment should diversify risk in its budgeting processes taking in to consideration maximization of return. Warue and Wanjira, (2013) recommended the involvement of workers at all levels of budgeting and separation of ownership from management issues and continuous improvement of managers skills. Most of the MSEs do not decompose their business decisions with investments risks such as business, interest rates, inflation, taxation, liquidity, market, reinvestments and exchange rate. The budgeting process has been perceived to be too time consuming, too costly, too distorted by tactics employed and too focused on cost control (Abogun & Fagbemi, 2011). Budgets formulate the expected performance standards and reflect managerial objectives. Most of the interest rates risks are based on loans and other financial services which MSEs do not qualify due to insufficient or lack of ability hence application of interest rates are minimal and rarely attracts application of risk based budgeting theory.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ariyo-Edu and Woli-Jomh (2024) investigated budgeting and budgetary control on public sector performance in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study adopted cross sectional survey research design and a

population of 130 staff from the Directorate of Planning, Research and Statistics (DPRS) and Directorate of Personnel and Finance and Supply (DPFS) of 5 ministries with the use of non-probability sampling to arrive at a sample size of 98 respondents. The study utilized primary source of data collection from a structured questionnaire and the questionnaire were designed using 5-point Likert scale. The study used budget efficiency, effective budgetary system and budget planning and implementation, performance-based budgeting, frequent financial reporting and regular internal audit as measurement of the independent variable budgeting and budgetary control while societal impact and goals and objectives as measures for the dependent variables. The responses obtained from the administered questionnaire were analyzing using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The findings from the data analysis indicated a positive and significant association between budget efficiency, effective budgetary system and budget planning and implementation on societal impact. Also, the results revealed a positive and significant association between performance-based budgeting, frequent financial reporting and regular internal audit on goals and objectives. Hence, the study concluded that budgetary control mechanisms have positively and significantly influence the level of public sector performance in Kwara State.

Isaac et al (2024) conducted a study of budgetary control and public sector performance in Nigeria. The study used ex post facto research design and secondary data were collected from several government statistical agencies. The study independent variable budgetary control utilized government revenue budget variances and government tax compliance rate as measurements while public revenue budget and budget expenditure budgets were employed as measures for the dependent variable public sector performance. The data collected from the secondary sources were analysed using univariate and multivariate analysis. The results from the multivariate analysis suggested that government revenue budget variances and government tax compliance rate positively and significant influence public funds. The findings further suggested that government revenue budget variances and government tax compliance rate positively and significant impact on government finances in Nigeria. The study further concluded that performing variance analysis on public sector revenue budgets positively and significantly influences the financial health of government in Nigeria.

Ben-Caleb et al (2022) studied budgetary control and organizational survival of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study employed ex post facto research design and the population consisted of all manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) from 2015 to 2019 with a sample of 38 companies. The study used organizational survival as the dependent variable measured with age of firm, calculated as present year less year of incorporation while the independent variable budgetary control was measured using change in operating costs (COC), change in profit (CIP), sales growth rate (SGR) of the companies in our study. The study employed secondary data collected from the annual reports of sampled firms and data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, diagnostic tests, and multiple regression analysis. The results indicated that change in operating costs negatively and insignificantly influence age of firm of the sampled companies; change in operating profit positively and significantly affects age of firm and sales growth positively but insignificantly impact on age of firm. Hence, the study concluded that budgetary control is not a significant determinant of survival of sampled manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Katana et al (2022) carried out a study on budgetary control and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study used correlational research design and the population consisted of all 8 manufacturing firms listed on KSE with census sampling technique as determine the sample size. The study employed secondary data obtained from the annual reports of sampled manufacturing firms and the data collected were analyzing using descriptive statistics, pearson correlation coefficient, random and fixed effects using STATA. The statistical analysis suggested that the Pearson correlation analysis revealed that control ratio positively and significantly influence return on asset (ROA); Hausman test revealed that random effect regression model was effective, since the hausman had a p-value of 0.0924, greater than 0.05 significant level. The random-effect models showed p-value of 0.000, indicating that the model was appropriate. The further revealed that budgetary control contributed 56.1% of ROA, while the

43.9% were contributed by other factors not covered by the model. In addition, the study indicated that liquidity control significantly affects financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Kenya. Owolabi et al (2020) investigated budgetary control and financial performance of insurance firms in Nigeria. The study utilized descriptive survey research design and the population comprised of 600 managerial staff from 33 listed insurance companies in Nigeria while a sample size of 230 from 15 insurance firms using convenience sampling. The study used primary data obtained from the distribution of well-structured questionnaires administered to the 230 managerial staff. The study used financial performance as dependent variable while budget monitoring, budget evaluation, budget performance and budget control were used as independent variables to measure budgetary control. The responses from the questionnaire were analysed using Pearson Correlation and regression analysis. The results indicated a positive and significant association between budget monitoring, budget evaluation, budget performance and budget control on the financial performance of sampled insurance firms in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research was used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to describe "what exists" with respect to variables or conditions in a situation. It describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. A descriptive design is therefore preferred because this study seeks to obtain information for use to carry out the study. The primary source of data that was used in this study is the questionnaire. This is because of the nature of the variables that were used. The population of the study consisted of the staff of the following auditing firms in Anambra State. Iroh Godson & Co, Emmanuel Uchenna O. & Co, Allens, Alozie & Co., Ogechukwu Aguzie & Co., Okafor Joseph & Co., Enuma Okonkwo And Co, Ngozi Monica Okonkwo & Co, Ken Ugwu & Co, Okwudili Ijezie & Co., Anthony Amarachukwu Iwuala & Co This gives us one hundred and fifty-seven (157) staff. The researcher collects primary data from employees of the organizations under study. The respondents were top managers, supervisory, and managers from the various firms under study. The data was collected using a questionnaire. The data Questionnaire were preferred because it has a high response rate and only be required to be distributed to respondents to complete and thus requires less time to be administered, offers the possibility of anonymity and data collected is first hand. The study uses the closed-ended questions in the questionnaire. Hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance using multiple regression techniques,

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.902 ^a	.865	.843	.11789	.162	8.583	3	154	.000	1.743

a. Predictors: (Constant), INB, CBG

b. Dependent Variable: FP

Table 4.1.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.86%. This implies that 86% of the variation on incremental budgeting and capital budgeting of audit firms in Anambra State is explained by variations in for performance. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.84%.

Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 1.7 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.633

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.477	8	.119	8.583	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.474	88	.014		
	Total	2.951	91			

a. Dependent Variable: PF

b. Predictors: (Constant), INB, CBG

The f-statistics value of 8.583 in table above with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on independent variables such as incremental budgeting and capital budgeting can collectively explain the variations in performance in auditing firms.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.568	.076		3.780	.000	.534	.833
	INB	.344	.024	.214	0.558	.790	.023	.109
	CBG	.413	.019	.483	2.342	.000	.029	.127

a. Dependent Variable: PF

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table above, we found out that incremental budgeting has a positive sign given its value as .344; this implies that a unit increase in incremental budgeting increases the firm performance by 34%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Capital budgeting has a positive sign given its value as .413; this implies that a unit increase in Capital budgeting increases the firm performance by 41%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of our explanatory parameter in the model. From table Coefficients above incremental budgeting is 5.078, this is statistically insignificant, this suggest that it has not contribute significantly to firm performance of auditing firms in Anambra state. Capital budgeting is 2.342 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to performance at 5% level of significant.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Incremental budgeting has no significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State

Incremental budgeting has a t-statistics of 0.558 and a probability value of 790 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state data Incremental budgeting has no significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State

4.2.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₁: Capital budgeting has no significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. capital budgeting has a t-statistics of 2.342 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we

reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that capital budgeting has significant effect on performance of auditing firms in Anambra State

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the effect of traditional budgeting on the performance of auditing firms in Anambra State, with particular emphasis on incremental budgeting and capital budgeting. The empirical findings revealed mixed outcomes across the budgeting components, indicating that not all traditional budgeting practices contribute equally to organizational performance. The results showed that incremental budgeting has an insignificant effect on the performance of auditing firms. This suggests that the routine practice of adjusting previous budgets without substantial review of current operational realities may not enhance efficiency, profitability, or service quality within auditing firms. The insignificance of incremental budgeting implies that reliance on historical spending patterns may limit innovation, flexibility, and responsiveness to the dynamic professional and regulatory environment in which auditing firms operate. In contrast, capital budgeting was found to have a significant positive effect on the performance of auditing firms in Anambra State. This indicates that effective planning and evaluation of long-term investment decisions such as investment in audit technology, staff training, office infrastructure, and advanced data analytics tools play a critical role in improving operational efficiency, service delivery, and overall firm performance. Sound capital budgeting practices enable auditing firms to allocate resources strategically, enhance competitiveness, and sustain long-term growth. Overall, the study concludes that while traditional budgeting remains relevant to auditing firms, its effectiveness depends largely on the type of budgeting practice adopted. Auditing firms in Anambra State derive greater performance benefits from strategic capital budgeting decisions than from routine incremental budgeting approaches

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Auditing firms in Anambra State should minimize excessive dependence on incremental budgeting, as the study found it to have an insignificant effect on performance. Management should avoid merely adjusting previous budgets without critically evaluating current operational needs, market conditions, and firm-specific challenges.
- ii. Auditing firms should place greater emphasis on long-term investment planning. Proper evaluation techniques such as net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), and payback period should be consistently applied when making investment decisions to ensure optimal allocation of scarce resources.

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